

Konso

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Entry tags: Religion, African Religions

"The Konso are comprised of three groups [regions] living in southern Ethiopia—the Garati, the Takadi, and the Turo..." (eHRAF World Cultures: Konso Culture Summary). The regions are each comprised of several semi-autonomous towns that possess a cultural unity based on allegiance to one of the great regional poqalla (religious/civil leaders), sacred drum cycles, and an age-grade system (Hallpike, 2008:88). The Konso do not have an official organized religion or political system, but share a set of common ideas, rituals, and conventions. For the Konso, religion and society are the intertwined assumptions, beliefs, and practices of life.

Date Range: 1920 CE - 1967 CE

Region: Rift Valley of Southern Ethiopia

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Ethiopia

The Konso territory is a range of mountains about fifty kilometers south of Lake Shamo, in a bend of the Sagan River in the Rift Valley of southern Ethiopia (eHRAF World Cultures, Konso Culture Summary). The Konso live in over 30 towns; this entry focuses on the more remote towns (mainly Buso) that were unaffected by missionary influence at the time of the principal ethnographer's account (1965-67).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/ehrafe/>

— Source 1 Description: eHRAF World Cultures: Konso (MP17)

— Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=mp17-004>

— Source 2 Description: Hallpike, C. R. (Christopher Robert). 2008. "Konso Of Ethiopia: A Study Of The Values Of An East Cushitic People." Central Milton Keynes: AuthorHouse.

Notes: Source 2: Hallpike visited the Konso from 1965-1967, and again in 1997. Hallpike made a point to gather information from isolated towns, such as Buso, in order to study "traditional beliefs and ceremonies unaffected by missionary influence" (p.21).

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: After Italian occupation of Ethiopia in the 1930's, Priests of the Ethiopian Orthodox Church claimed to baptize the Konso. However, the Konso resisted this Christian influence and feared it would affect their traditional religious beliefs. Later in 1954, the Norwegian Lutheran Mission, associated with the Ethiopian Evangelical Church of Mekane (House of) Yesus (EECMY), established a mission in Konso territory. Like earlier attempts, the Konso did not accept the Christian influence, and were initially hostile towards the newcomers. Additionally, there were tensions between the Orthodox and Lutheran missions (Hallpike, 2008, chapter 1). The Konso as a society also had contact with, and was absorbed by the Ethiopian Empire which, "until recently, was dominated by the Amhara of Shoa Province, at whose head was the Emperor himself" (Hallpike, 2008:4). The Konso and Amhara's relationship as neighboring societies was volatile and aggressive. During the 1930's the Konso experienced a period of Italian occupation. The Konso and Italian's relationship was fairly neutral. Within the Konso society itself, individual towns occasionally fought one another.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The Konso had a competitive relationship with the Orthodox and Lutherans. After the Italian occupation of Ethiopia in the 1930's, Priests of the Ethiopian Orthodox Church claimed to baptize the Konso. However, the Konso resisted this Christian influence and feared it would affect their traditional religious beliefs. Later in 1954, the Norwegian Lutheran Mission, associated with the Ethiopian Evangelical Church of Mekane (House of) Yesus (EECMY), established a mission in Konso territory. Like earlier attempts, the Konso did not accept the Christian influence, and were initially hostile towards the newcomers. Additionally, there were tensions between the Orthodox and Lutheran missions (Hallpike, 2008, chapter 1).

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: After initial hostility towards the Norwegian Lutheran Mission, the Konso developed a more accommodating relationship with the Mission. During the 1960's, the Konso were pleased to have a school and clinic, and enjoyed a less-hostile relationship with the Amhara as a result of the Mission's presence. Additionally, the Konso slowly began to adopt the Christian faith into their own belief systems (Hallpike, 2008:19-20).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 1960 CE

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: While the Konso had a neutral relationship with the Italians, this was not the case with the Orthodox, Lutherans, and Amhara.

– Yes

Notes: The Konso, in a sense, welcomed Italian military presence as a blockade to violent interactions with the Amhara. Additionally, land transportation infrastructure was constructed during the Italian occupation (Hallpike, 2008, chapter 1).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Although Konso towns would occasionally fight, "unregulated violence is only one aspect of the relationships between the towns, for they are often united in longstanding alliances" (Hallpike, 2008:103).

– Yes

Notes: Occasionally, individual towns within the Konso society fought one another (Hallpike, 2008:98-102).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: Although the Konso had, at times, tensions with the Italian occupation and later mission groups, these tensions did not result in outright warfare (Hallpike, 2008, chapter 1).

– Yes

Notes: "During this period [1896-1965] the Konso were absorbed into the Ethiopian Empire which, until very recently, has been dominated by the Amhara of Shoa Province, at whose head was the Emperor himself" (Hallpike, 2008:4). The Amhara conquest of the Konso was violent, and produced lasting tensions (Hallpike, 2008, chapter 1).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The Konso do not have a formal, organized religion. Rather, the Konso are connected in a set of shared beliefs, ritual organization, ceremonies, and a cycle of sacred drums. There is no formal process for assigning religious affiliation. As the principal authority and ethnographic source states, "the Konso have no professional theologians or other learned specialists who can give an authoritative insight into their religious beliefs. When I say "beliefs", I do not mean that the Konso are aware of the possibilities of unbelief and so "believe" in God in the sense employed by Christians saying the Creed. There is no Konso word for "to believe", and Mission translations of the Gospels borrow the Amharic word ammanna. What I call their beliefs are simply some unquestioned assumptions about their world. The evidence for these consists of a few myths, a considerable body of ritual, and statements by the people themselves, and we must be careful not to distort this fragile and elusive material by forcing it into inappropriate categories such as "monotheism", or trying to make hard-and-fast distinctions between "religion" and "society", or between "religion" and "magic". For example the Konso, like other East Cushitic peoples, believe in the Sky-God Waqa, but it is quite misleading to represent Waqa as the Creator in the Judaeo-Christian tradition, and the Konso religion as straightforward monotheism, just as it is difficult to say to what extent Waqa is for them a "personal" deity" (Hallpike, 2008:288).

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The Konso society is led by regional figures, called poqalla. Regional poqalla are the head of a lineage, and typically oversee several towns, each with their own local poqalla. In addition to holding an office and having public responsibilities, regional poqalla are priests, with special supernatural powers and responsibilities. Because the regional poqalla are both religious and civil leaders, the religion, in a sense, has political support. However, the Konso have neither an organized political system, nor an organized religious system. Because there is no clear political unity among the Konso, the religion cannot be said to have political support. (See Hallpike, 2008, Chapter Ix, Section 7).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Konso are almost unique in traditional Ethiopia for living in densely populated walled towns holding on average about 1,500 people. The principal ethnographic source estimated Buso to have a population of about 1,545 in 1965, assuming the average household to be 5 persons (Hallpike, 2008:113).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 100

Notes: The Konso do not have an organized religion, but are connected through a set of shared beliefs, rituals, age-groupings, and sacred drum cycles. In this way, all members of the Konso society adhere to the same religious system. (Hallpike, 2008:288).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Konso are organized by clans, lineages, and regions. Each lineage has a head--a poqalla--who is also a priestly figure. Local poqualla are the heads of their lineages in each town, but have no wider authority (Hallpike, 2008:72). The most prominent leaders are regional poqalla. "The poqalla, who inherit their office by primogeniture in the male line, are lineage heads and men of wealth who also have essential religious duties. Major poqalla also act as priests and mediators at a regional level within Konso" (Hallpike, 2008:66). "...we can refer to the ritual organization of the regions, with a great priest, a distinctive generation grading system embracing all the towns in the region, and an associated set of ceremonies, and a cycle of sacred drums..." (Hallpike, 2008:106). "The poqalla is therefore the religious as well as the genealogical and economic focus of the lineage, since his essential duty is to bring Life - health, fertility, and peace - to its members. This he does in two ways, by preventing the outbreak of serious quarrels among its members by mediating in their disputes, and by officiating at two ceremonies at the beginning of the great rains, called the Arxata Ayla and the Lokayta" (Hallpike, 2008:179).

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Regional poqalla oversee all towns and local poqalla within their jurisdiction (Hallpike, 2008:72).

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: Regional poqalla oversee all towns and local poqalla within their jurisdiction (Hallpike, 2008:72).

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 2

Notes: Regional poqalla oversee all towns and local poqalla within their jurisdiction (Hallpike, 2008:72).

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "The basic functions of the poqalla are therefore to bless his lineage and perform religious ceremonies, usually involving sacrifice, and to settle their disputes, and he may also use the sanction of the curse. Miraculous origins and deeds are often attributed to poqalla ancestors and figure prominently in the legends about them" (Hallpike, 2008:178).

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

Notes: "...a poqalla as priest does not need to have any special knowledge, to be remarkable in any way for his occult attainments, or to have a personal relationship with a supernatural being" (Hallpike, 2008:342).

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

Notes: "...a poqalla as priest does not need to have any special knowledge, to be remarkable in any way for his occult attainments, or to have a personal relationship with a supernatural being" (Hallpike, 2008:342).

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: "The poqalla, who inherit their office by primogeniture in the male line, are lineage heads and men of wealth who also have essential religious duties. Major poqalla also act as priests and mediators at a regional level within Konso" (Hallpike, 2008:66). "I define a priest as someone who, by virtue of his office, can confer benefits by supernatural means on his religious dependants" (Hallpike, 2008:342).

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: "The poqalla, who inherit their office by primogeniture in the male line, are lineage heads and men of wealth who also have essential religious duties. Major poqalla also act as priests and mediators at a regional level within Konso" (Hallpike, 2008:66).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "The body is simply flesh, soa, which is buried at death. Soa is also the word used for animal meat, which one buys in the market. The breath is nesa, and at death this is taken by God [note: "God" refers to Waqa]. Vitality, which is in practice the pulse, especially as seen beating below the ribs, is lupota, and this simply disappears when a man dies. The soul is kelelayta, or katilayta, which is also the word for shadow. Katilayta is really a compound of the word kata meaning shade, and the suffix -olayta, meaning "a person"; thus the whole word means "shade person". Kelelayta means "inside person". At death the soul finally leaves the body and pursues an independent existence as a ghost, kariiya. The only difference between a katilayta and a kariiya is that the katilayta still belongs to a living body, which it leaves at night in dreams, but to which it finally returns, while a kariiya no longer has a body" (Hallpike, 2008:303).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The soul of a living person can leave the body at night in dreams (Hallpike, 2008:303).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "The body is simply flesh, soa, which is buried at death. Soa is also the word used for animal meat, which one buys in the market. The breath is nesa, and at death this is taken by God. Vitality, which is in practice the pulse, especially as seen beating below the ribs, is lupota, and this simply disappears when a man dies. The soul is kelelayta, or katilayta, which is also the word for shadow. Katilayta is really a compound of the word kata meaning shade, and the suffix -olayta, meaning "a person"; thus the whole word means "shade person". Kelelayta means "inside person". At death the soul finally leaves the body and pursues an independent existence as a ghost, kariiya. The only difference between a katilayta and a kariiya is that the katilayta still belongs to a living body, which it leaves at night in dreams, but to which it finally returns, while a kariiya no longer has a body" (Hallpike, 2008:303).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Death is the end of human existence as they think of it, and the afterlife for them is the usual drab and bat-like existence envisaged by so many pagan peoples" (Hallpike, 2008:378).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: "The Konso have little idea of the kind of life that the ghosts lead; but certainly there is no belief in any separate abode or punishments for evildoers, and rewards for the good. Sinners are punished by sickness or death in this life, and after death there is just a common batlike existence for all" (Hallpike, 2008:300).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: See Hallpike, 2008, section 10. Earth and Death

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "The graves are about 5 ft. deep, and of oblong plan, about 3 ft. by 1½ ft. At the bottom is a lateral niche, cut in the long side of the hole, in which the body is placed. This is done specifically to prevent the earth falling on the corpse itself. In some areas a smaller hole is made at the bottom of the shaft, in which the corpse lies covered with timbers" (Hallpike, 2008:380).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: "The body was placed firmly in a crouching position, with the hands clasped on the breast. In Garati [a town] only grandfathers and grandmothers are supposed to be buried in this position, other people being interred in the extended position" (Hallpike, 2008:380).

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: "The body was placed firmly in a crouching position, with the hands clasped on the breast. In Garati [a town] only grandfathers and grandmothers are supposed to be buried in this position, other people being interred in the extended position" (Hallpike, 2008:380).

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Poqalla (civil/religious leaders) are buried in a temporary grave within the homestead for three years, and then "exhumed and either reburied in the family cemetery in the fields or,

if it is a regional poqalla, in his juniper wood" (Hallpike, 2008:382). Additionally, the poqalla's intestines are removed, placed in a separate pot, and interred beside the body (ibid).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: "Nothing is usually buried with corpses..." (Hallpike, 2008:381).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: See Hallpike, 2008:168, and section 10. Earth and Death

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "When a person dies, he or she is carried out into the fields and buried the same day" (Hallpike, 2008:378). Note-in the town of Turo, corpses are buried in groves of trees (ibid, page 377).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The most powerful and central supernatural being is Waqa, followed by the Earth and Sun. Also present are ghosts, evil spirits, and minor spirits (such as well spirits). (See Hallpike, 2008, Chapter IX).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "...the Konso, like other East Cushitic peoples, believe in the Sky-God Waqa, but it is quite misleading to represent Waqa as the Creator in the Judaeo-Christian tradition, and the Konso religion as straightforward monotheism, just as it is difficult to say to what extent Waqa is for them a "personal" deity. Waqa, or God as I shall call him for convenience, is seen as the author of the social order, but the responsibility of maintaining this is thought to have been delegated to men, and especially to the elders by God when he went away" (Hallpike, 2008:288).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "...the Konso, like other East Cushitic peoples, believe in the Sky-God Waqa..." (Hallpike, 2008:288).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: "...the Konso, like other East Cushitic peoples, believe in the Sky-God Waqa..." (Hallpike, 2008:288).

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Atmospheric phenomena (e.g., rain, thunder)

Notes: "Waqa is the Sky-God and the source of rain: when it rains the Konso do not just say "It is raining", but "Waqa is raining", and certain phenomena associated with rain, such as thunder and lightning and rainbows, are regarded as manifestations of his power" (Hallpike, 2008:289).

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "...Waqa still keeps a close eye on what goes on among the Konso, and acts accordingly" (Hallpike, 2008:294). However, the degree of attention to human activity and morality may not be very substantial, as Waqa (God), "is seen as the author of the social order, but the responsibility of maintaining this is thought to have been delegated to men, and especially to the elders by God when he went away" (Hallpike, 2008:288).

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: "For ordinary Konso, God's punishments apply, in particular, to boundary disputes, and Waqa is believed to intervene directly when two men are disputing over the ownership of a piece of land" (Hallpike, 2008:295).

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Waqa is a god not only of rain, but of justice, who punishes towns that are guilty of too much quarrelling and animosity by withholding the rain from their fields" (Hallpike, 2008:292).

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "Waqa is a god not only of rain, but of justice, who punishes towns that are guilty of too much quarrelling and animosity by withholding the rain from their fields" (Hallpike, 2008:292).

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Although Waqa is the most powerful entity, The Earth is an important cosmological entity independent of and complementary to Waqa (Hallpike, 2008:289).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The body is simply flesh, soa, which is buried at death. Soa is also the word used for animal meat, which one buys in the market. The breath is nesa, and at death this is taken by God. Vitality, which is in practice the pulse, especially as seen beating below the ribs, is lupota, and this simply disappears when a man dies. The soul is kelelayta, or katilayta, which is also the word for shadow. Katilayta is really a compound of the word kata meaning shade, and the suffix -olayta, meaning "a person"; thus the whole word means "shade person". Kelelayta means "inside person". At death the soul finally leaves the body and pursues an independent existence as a ghost, kariiya. The only difference between a katilayta and a kariiya is that the katilayta still belongs to a living body, which it leaves at night in dreams, but to which it finally returns, while a kariiya no longer has a body" (Hallpike, 2008:303).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "...it is said that some diviners can see the souls of men in the daytime and talk with them" (Hallpike, 2008:303).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "...it is said that some diviners can see the souls of men in the daytime and talk with them" (Hallpike, 2008:303).

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: "They[ghosts] are thought still to be in contact with their surviving relatives and descendants, returning in dreams either to the lineage poqalla [civil/religious leader] or their immediate surviving relatives, and especially when a person dies he or she will return a short time after death, in a dream, to demand the sacrifice of a bull, which will be carried out" (Hallpike, 2008:300).

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Notes: While specialists (diviners) can communicate with the deceased, others may as well (see previous question on spirit communication through dreams). "...it is said that some diviners can see the souls of men in the daytime and talk with them" (Hallpike, 2008:303).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The Earth, piita, is therefore an independent cosmological entity which is responsible for the growth of plants, crops, and trees, and for all animal and human life" (Hallpike, 2008:289).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Generally, like the ghosts, evil spirits only come out after dark, when they may perhaps be seen as bright lights moving out in the fields" (Hallpike, 2008:298).

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: The following is an anecdotal example of an evil spirit entering the body and causing pain: "One of Sagara Gaya's [informant] wives complained that an evil spirit was in the habit of sitting just outside her grindinghouse, giving her severe backache as she worked the stones (Normally, of course, women feel no aches and pains when working the grindstones as they are used to it)" (Hallpike, 2008:298).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "The Earth, piita, is therefore an independent cosmological entity which is responsible for the growth of plants, crops, and trees, and for all animal and human life" (Hallpike, 2008:289).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Evil spirits are strongly associated with the condition of insanity, and possession is attributed to them, and them only" (Hallpike, 2008:298).

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Evil spirits are not exactly punishing. These spirits are malicious beings that seem to harm for the sake of harming. (See Hallpike, 2008, Chapter 2. Waqa and the Social Order, section 3: Evil Spirits and Ghosts)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "...Waqa still keeps a close eye on what goes on among the Konso, and acts accordingly"

(Hallpike, 2008:294).

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "Waqqa, then, is certainly seen as a father-figure, not so much in the sense of the begetter of the human race, but as the source of morality" (Hallpike, 2008:297).

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: See Hallpike, 2008, page 295

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: See Hallpike, 2008, page 295

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: "Waqqa is a god not only of rain, but of justice, who punishes towns that are guilty of too much quarrelling and animosity by withholding the rain from their fields" (Hallpike, 2008:292).

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: "For ordinary Konso, God's punishments apply, in particular, to boundary disputes, and Waqqa is believed to intervene directly when two men are disputing over the ownership of a piece of land" (Hallpike, 2008:295).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "Waqqa is a god not only of rain, but of justice, who punishes towns that are guilty of too much quarrelling and animosity by withholding the rain from their fields" (Hallpike, 2008:292).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence for supernatural punishment points to Waqqa as the agent of justice and "the source and maintainer of the moral and social order" (Hallpike, 2008:292). It is not explicitly stated that Waqqa is the only agent of punishment, but there is no direct evidence for any other supernatural being inflicting punishment.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence for supernatural punishment points to Waqa as the agent of justice and "the source and maintainer of the moral and social order" (Hallpike, 2008:292). It is not explicitly stated that Waqa is the only agent of punishment, but there is no direct evidence for any other supernatural being inflicting punishment.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, supernatural punishment is done to enforce moral and social order. "Waqa, then, is certainly seen as a father-figure, not so much in the sense of the begetter of the human race, but as the source of morality" (Hallpike, 2008:297).

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, supernatural punishment is done to enforce moral and social order. "Waqa, then, is certainly seen as a father-figure, not so much in the sense of the begetter of the human race, but as the source of morality" (Hallpike, 2008:297).

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

Notes: Evil spirits are malicious spirits that randomly attack humans for no clear reason, often invoking fear in the Konso people (see Hallpike, 2008, Chapter 2, Section 3).

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Done to promote social cohesion. "Waqa is a god not only of rain, but of justice, who punishes towns that are guilty of too much quarrelling and animosity by withholding the rain from their fields" (Hallpike, 2008:292).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: "The Konso have little idea of the kind of life that the ghosts lead; but certainly there is no belief in any separate abode or punishments for evildoers, and rewards for the good. Sinners are punished by sickness or death in this life, and after death there is just a common batlike existence for all" (Hallpike, 2008:300).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "The Konso have little idea of the kind of life that the ghosts lead; but certainly there is

no belief in any separate abode or punishments for evildoers, and rewards for the good. Sinners are punished by sickness or death in this life, and after death there is just a common batlike existence for all" (Hallpike, 2008:300).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: "Waqā is a god not only of rain, but of justice, who punishes towns that are guilty of too much quarrelling and animosity by withholding the rain from their fields" (Hallpike, 2008:292).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: "The Konso have little idea of the kind of life that the ghosts lead; but certainly there is no belief in any separate abode or punishments for evildoers, and rewards for the good. Sinners are punished by sickness or death in this life, and after death there is just a common batlike existence for all" (Hallpike, 2008:300).

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: "The Konso have little idea of the kind of life that the ghosts lead; but certainly there is no belief in any separate abode or punishments for evildoers, and rewards for the good. Sinners are punished by sickness or death in this life, and after death there is just a common batlike existence for all" (Hallpike, 2008:300).

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in the sense that the Konso "religion" and "society" are one in the same. The Konso have social norms and behaviors that are expected to be upheld. (see Hallpike, 2008 Chapter 2 Waqa and the Social Order, and Chapter VI: Konso Values).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Konso religion and society are coterminous, and all social norms and behaviors are expected to be upheld. However, there are both conventional norms (such as cleanliness practices) and moral rules (such as an incest taboo). (see Hallpike, 2008 Chapter 2 Waqa and the Social Order, and Chapter VI: Konso Values).

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: (see Hallpike, 2008 Chapter 2 Waqa and the Social Order, and Chapter VI: Konso

Values).

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: see below for specific details

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Notes: "There are, however, certain forms of social behaviour which are thought to incur death but without the agency of divine intervention. For a young woman to approach an ulahita would be very dangerous for Xrela, and when some Christian Konso girls, working at the Mission in the early 1960s, decided to flout this taboo in Patankalto they were arrested by the infuriated elders, but there is no question of God being offended in such cases; women are dangerous to the ulahita, as we have seen, because of the harmful effect of their sexuality on the symbol of the warrior grade" (Hallpike, 2008:287).

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: "A poqalla's old homestead, and his wood, if he has one, are sacred, and it is forbidden to cut them; someone who did so would be liable to go mad, but this is not a divine punishment but simply a mystical consequence" (Hallpike, 2008:297).

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: "Waqqa, then, is certainly seen as a father-figure, not so much in the sense of the begetter of the human race, but as the source of morality" (Hallpike, 2008:297).

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Because the Konso religious system and political/civil system are coterminous, virtues are of both religious and socio-cultural importance. See Hallpike, 2008, Chapter VI: Konso Values

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: "Dukaata, "truth", is a very important moral concept for the Konso that is closely allied to the ideals of peace and discussion: apart from meaning a statement that is factually correct it

implies the opposite of the lie, and therefore connotes honesty and uprightness in general. The Konso are typical of tribal societies and early states in the great importance they ascribe to this concept, because truth is one of the essential components of order. When all speak the truth harmony is possible, whereas the lie is one of the chief sources of disorder and confusion and the liar is the anti-social person who breaks the rules. The truth is also the predictable, the reliable, and that which makes cooperation possible, but the Konso concede the frailty of human nature in this respect when they refer to the grave as the porra dukaata, "the way of truth", because only the dead tell no lies" (Hallpike, 2008:220).

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: see Hallpike, 2008:346

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: See Hallpike, 2008, Chapter VI: Konso Values

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: Cooperation is an extremely important value to the Konso. See Hallpike, 2008, Chapter VI: Konso Values

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: See Hallpike, 2008, Chapter VI: Konso Values

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in the sense of respecting leaders such as the regional poqalla. See Hallpike, 2008, Chapter VI: Konso Values

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Peace

Notes: See Hallpike, 2008, Chapter VI: Konso Values

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is forbidden to eat any kind of bird or their eggs, but it is unclear why this taboo is in place and if it has any religious/ritual association (Hallpike, 2008:37).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: "We must therefore approach Konso religion primarily through ritual and symbolism. The most important type of ritual is the killana, which has the following elements: The sacrifice of a consecrated beast (bullock, he-goat, or ram). The anointing of the participants, especially with hansapita and butter. Prayers and blessings" (Hallpike, 2008:206). (note: Hallpike goes on to describe several rituals in specific detail)

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Orthodoxy checks are present in the sense that significant rituals are led by specialists (Hallpike, 2008, Chapter V, Section 2; Chapter IX, Section 6).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: The Konso society is best described as a very informal chiefdom. The Konso are organized by semi-autonomous towns, each possessing a local civil/religious leader (poqalla). Regional poqalla oversee several towns, which are connected by age-groups, ceremonies, ritual observances, and a sacred drum cycle. Regional poqalla intercede when needed (e.g., to settle a large dispute or perform a ritual). The Konso are not connected above the regional level in either a political or religious sense. (See Hallpike, 2008, various pages).

Education

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: A government school was established around 1966 by the Norwegian Lutheran Mission (Hallpike, 2008:18).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: There is no formal bureaucracy among the Konso (see Hallpike, 2008, various sections).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored by individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: "The Elbola stream below Buso, which runs all the year round, is used for irrigating a few gardens. Elaborate stone leats or kapa allow the water to pass through series of walled gardens, which grow prolific crops of taro, yam, banana, papaya, and potatoes, as well as maize and sorghum and a little ensete. But such amenities are very rare, and this type of permanent irrigation is quite untypical" (Hallpike, 2008:42).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: "These were still nothing more than rough mule tracks at best, with no bridges over the many rivers, and the only means of transporting goods were baggage animals and human carriers. In these conditions it would obviously have been impossible to send significant quantities of taxes in the form of goods all the way to Addis Ababa, and it follows that in so far as taxes were paid in kind they must have been consumed by the local Amhara" (Hallpike, 2008:12).

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: During Italian military occupation ca. 1930's, roads were built (Hallpike, 2008:16).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: The Konso do not have an organized religious or political system to levy taxes or tithes. However, individual town leaders or religious specialists may occasionally require taxes. "Traditionally, the councils [group of town leaders, usually comprised of several older and respected men] could call on the support of the warrior grade, Xrela, to arrest and punish criminals, and to enforce their decisions.

These councils debate issues of general concern – without being able to violate public opinion – and act as a court of justice. It was and still is the custom for councillors and shorokta [religious practitioners] to receive a tribute in the form of a harvest tax (maala). The organization of the council varies from town to town..." (Hallpike, 2008:116).

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The Imperial Government had therefore appointed a separate system of tax collection directly controlled by the Ministry of Finance and Commerce in Addis Ababa. Each Province had a Nagadras ("Chief of the Merchants"), under whom were the Chikashums, or market-chiefs, in every town that had a market. These officials "levy a tenth on the annual production and collect this after the harvest, naturally mostly in kind. During the markets they collect a kind of sales tax, and contracts of purchase and sale are also subject to duty" (ibid., 180), and the proceeds were transmitted by the Nagadras to Addis Ababa. There were also customs posts on the borders of each district whose revenues were paid to the local governor. The currency in which taxes were collected was the Maria Theresa dollar and it must be pointed out that by this time a good deal of money was coming into circulation, since it would have been extremely difficult to levy large amounts of taxes in kind because of the lack of proper roads. These were still nothing more than rough mule tracks at best, with no bridges over the many rivers, and the only means of transporting goods were baggage animals and human carriers. In these conditions it would obviously have been impossible to send significant quantities of taxes in the form of goods all the way to Addis Ababa, and it follows that in so far as taxes were paid in kind they must have been consumed by the local Amhara" (Hallpike, 2008:12).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "Thus the regional priests, the grading systems, and the sacred drums could supply only a moral, and not a political unity, although we should not underestimate the importance that this cultural unity of the region had for the maintenance of peace. As I mentioned earlier, the nearest equivalent to a police force exists in Garati only..." (Hallpike, 2008:97). "Traditionally, the councils could call on the support of the warrior grade, Xrela, to arrest and punish criminals, and to enforce their decisions. These councils debate issues of general concern – without being able to violate public opinion – and act as a court of justice. The organization of the council varies from town to town..." (Hallpike, 2008:116). "In each town there is a drum, which is usually held for one year (but occasionally for more than this) by a poqalla [civil/religious leader] or shorokta [religious practitioner] in Xrela grade, who is one of an official cycle of drum-holders. Xrela are extremely important as the effective maintainers of law and order within the towns..." (Hallpike, 2008:124). "In each town there is a body of men who are the peacemakers, Apa Dawra, or Nama Dawra. Apa means "father", or more generally "adult male who has married and begotten children", and Nama means "person". Dawra is a contraction of idawrani, "he forbids". It is the job of these men to run between the quarrelling factions and cast down their staves of office on the ground to separate them" (Hallpike, 2008:128).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Individual towns could use the town council (a group of leaders, usually older and respected

men of the community) to act as a "justice system". If necessary, the regional leader (poqalla) would intervene. Additionally, the cycle of sacred drums is a symbol of peace and order, and the drum holder (prominent families would hold a drum for about a year before passing it on) could act as an agent of justice and morality. (Hallpike, 2008:94). "Traditionally, the councils could call on the support of the warrior grade, Xrela, to arrest and punish criminals, and to enforce their decisions. These councils debate issues of general concern – without being able to violate public opinion – and act as a court of justice. The organization of the council varies from town to town..." (Hallpike, 2008:116).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Among the Konso, punishment varied from town to town (Hallpike, 2008:116). Sources of justice and punishment could include a town council (a group of leaders, usually older and respected men of the community), the regional leader (poqalla), sacred drum holder, or warrior grade. (Hallpike, 2008:94, 116).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: (See Hallpike, 2008, various pages such as 96,106, 116, 214).

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Traditionally there was only one word for actions which we should distinguish as crimes and sins, dupota. Since the coming of the Amhara and their courts, however, criminals who are punishable under the new Ethiopian laws (and which, where they are offences against the person or property, were also punished in traditional Konso society) are called wenjeleta, from the Amharic wanjal, a crime" (Hallpike, 2008:296).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: See Hallpike, 2008:18

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: "Time reckoning is an important aspect of Konso culture and a very significant feature of their sense of cosmic and social order. It forms an essential basis for the gada systems, which are not only governed by sacred numbers but also perform the function of a social calendar. Their year is based on a cycle of 12 lunar months and each month, according to the people, has 30 days. Each month begins with the new moon, and the month is divided into two halves, corresponding to the waxing and

waning periods of the moon" (Hallpike, 2008:235).The Konso also have an agricultural calendar and ritual calendars (Hallpike, 2008, Chapter VII: Time Reckoning).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Konso religion and society are coterminous, and thus, provide food for themselves. The Konso are intensive agriculturalists, using manure, terracing, and simple agricultural tools such as hoes. Animal husbandry provides considerable subsistence as well. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Konso religion and society are coterminous, and thus, provide food for themselves. The Konso are intensive agriculturalists, using manure, terracing, and simple agricultural tools such as hoes. Animal husbandry provides considerable subsistence as well. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.